

Flightlines for Copper Joe Creek, Eastern Denali Fault

Flight path (black lines) with the resultant DTM. Red stars indicate takeoff and landing locations for the collection(s). Satellite imagery from Google.

Note: the 2021 flight lines were calculated with a field of view of 60° (resulting in a narrower spacing), whereas the 2022 collections used a 90° field of view.